

The Influence of Credit Distributions Micro, Small and Middle (SMES) and Third Party Funds to Noperational Profit to Public Credit Bank Cirebon District

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Abstract: This research re euml xamine of what has been done by other researcher with the object of research on what is different aimed at peaceful and steady to analyze the good vibes this partial as well as simultaneous the amount of its credits micro small and medium enterprises (SMES) and prepare the funds to a third party against operating profit in public credit bank Cirebon district.

The results of the testing of hypotheses first discovered that variable credit small and medium enterprises 0.5456 or by 54,56 % show is influence against operating profit. The results of the testing of hypotheses to two variable third party funds of savings of 0.52134 or by 52,13 % show is influence against operating profit. The results of the testing of hypotheses to three variable third party funds in deposits of 0.5612 or by 56,12 % show is influence against operating profit.

All of the results of the analysis showed in constant of 0.5905 or 59.05%. This credit public bank Cirebon district contribute to the development and growth the small and medium enterprises (SMES) that is in Cirebon district and the rest is the other factors that to affect in out of what researchers do.

Key words: Credit, Small and Medium Enterprises, Funds and Operating Profit

I. Introduction

Law No 10 years 1998 date November 10, 1998 on banking, can be concluded that banking business includes three activities, namely raised funds, channel funds and give other banking services. Activities gather and disbursing funds is main activities bank while grant the services of bank others are program support. activities raised funds of raise funds of people in the form of savings giro, Savings and deposit accounts. Usually while being given it services pull it like, flowers and a gift as support for the community. Activities channel funds, for the provision of loans to the community while banking services others were given to support smooth the activity the main.

The role of the domestic banking industry the economy is the very vital especially money circulates in traffic. Among so many banking, the presence of public credit bank that provides financial products which is similar to that of conventional banks, it turns out having penetration who is better than the banking another especially to micro small medium enterprises.

Characteristic of public credit bank to have easy in credit distribution compared with a bank conventional another into attraction, so that credit bank the people still interested in. Segmentation bank market credit the people who sell their products to the community small and SMES is expected to be the key reason BPR can stay until now.

While the number of credit distribution BPR to the community showed the upward trend in. But, it happened still relatively small of number of loans were distributed by banking to SMES. The role of BPR as

an intermediating institution which is easily reached by public business until to rural areas is expected to grow of developed and increase the competitiveness of SMES.

Bank Indonesia in 2006 ago suggest to enhance the role of BPR in the provision of services to SMES is to strengthen BPR institutional with a variety of factors including funding structure, human resources, tastes consumers, supporting infrastructure, and operational BPR efficient. Because competition where more rigorous BPR currently must compete with funding units such as public banks, cooperatives and pawnshops.

Table 1
The development of credit credits bank perkreditasi rakyat

Years	Credit Distribution	Description	%
2010	Rp. 2.671.962.262	-	-
2011	Rp. 2.796.853.722	Increase of	0.05
2012	Rp. 3.324.363.865	Increase of	0.19
2013	Rp. 3.945.946.204	Increase of	0.19
2014	Rp. 5.500.982.524	Increase of	0.39

Source: skunder processed data

From the data obtained from it can be seen that the amount given by a company increased in every year. Lending activities was the largest banking sector, hence credit management to do better. Of credit activity, bank will have operational income in the form of interest income, and the provisi. Interest income is the largest source of income from the bank (Wijaya, 2005: 23). Interest income would come from any credit repayments paid by a debtor within the period agreed, usually every month. Every credit repayments paid, including some in loan principal coupled with some flowers. While provisi income obtained when the credit, of a certain percentage of credit granted.

Derive profit is the main objective of the establishment of a financial institutions including banks and other financial institutions. Profit obtained not only used to finance company operations, but also used to expand oil forthcoming as establishment branches. And more importantly when a financial institutions constantly derive profit, so this means survival a company will be guaranteed. Because largest activity banks are on the credit, but this activity determining the profit to be obtained in a period of. Profit is a most intense user because the expected profit rich enough to represent the company performance as a whole.

In achieving profit, companies should continue trying to gather third party funds to finance the their credits. Of any purpose the company is to achieve optimal profit, capital proven significantly have had a positive impact on the growth of profit. This indicates that the utilization of capital optimal caused earning obtained optimal, who eventually causing profit growth positive. While profit growth is percentile increase the profit obtained company. The financial performance of corporations is how the company to sustain and tense business profit, performance assessment is one of the ways carried out by the management to meet duties to accomplish its intended purpose the company is also used management in a decision-making. Good profit growth is cue the company performance good. A result of growth profit good will me.

II. Literature Review

Credit

Low No. 10 years 1998 said that the is the provision of money or bill that can be the same with it, under the approval of or an agreement and loan borrow between bank with other parties which requires the lender to settle his debt after a certain period of time by the provision of flowers. If someone use the credit, and he will worn flowers bills.

Savings

According to Law No 10 of 1998 on banking, savings is saving that withdrawals can be made only according to an agreed set of certain conditions, but not be drawn with a check, bilyet giro, and or other tool in equate with it.

Deposits

The decline in the deposit or that which are often called as a deposit the bank will issue later, is the product had not experienced a similar bank savings services that was already accustomed is offered to the public. The decline in the deposit fund raising in regard of underwritten by the government through one month deposits amounting to assurance agency to certain requirements **Operational Profit**

Operating profit was the result of the activity of of the hidden from among the company plan unless there a major change in economics, can hope to soon to be accomplished every year (Islahuzzaman, 2012: 238).

III. Research Methodology

Regression Analysis Linear Multiple.

It is anticipated that analysis of multiple regression is the method statistika used to determine the possibility of the form of (from) of the relations between variables. It is anticipated that analysis of multiple regression are used to obtain the regression coefficient that will be determine whether a hypothesis that is made is to be received or refused to play host to. The purpose of the author and source of in the use of this method is to foresee and estimate the value of one variable another to which it is be researched with the formula as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + e$$

Figure; 1. Model the Framework of Conception

IV. The Results and the Discussion

- The influence of credit to operational profit the calculation on obtained table linear regression multiple, statistically significant show results on the value probability credit smaller than α ($0.0000 < 0,05$) so can be concluded that variable credit significant and positive on operational profit on public credit bank Cirebon district.
- The influence of savings to operational profit the calculation on obtained table linear regression multiple, statistically significant show results on the value probability savings smaller than α ($0.0000 < 0.05$), so can be concluded that variable savings significant to operational profit on public credit bank Cirebon district
- The influence of deposits to operating profit results of which were found the table linear regression and the worship of idols, statistics show in significant results are in the value of the probability deposits

smaller than α ($0.0000 < 0.05$), so it can be concluded that the variable deposits significant and give a positive response to operating profit in public credit bank Cirebon district.

In the regression by using the method ordinary least square (OLS), obtained value the regression coefficient for every variable in the research by equation as follows:

$$Y = 0.5905 + 0.5456X_1 + 0.52134X_2 + 0.5612X_3$$

Figure 2. Regression testing shows and Coefficients of Determination

1. The influence of lending to operating profit from the credit regression found that significant and positive on operating profit on public credit bank Cirebon. Every bank is trying to continue to increase their profits, because the largest banks are on the credit, then credit have a direct impact towards operating profit obtained bank during a period. Credit operating income generation of interest income, provisi, the commission etc, besides credit also has risk of loan defaults that is a component burden for the bank, because banks potentially would not get interest income and some credit basic which has been distributed. Built with the sweat of statement have been further strengthened by the theory that was mentioned by these Kasmir (2005: 71) who said thursday he that banks faced problems with playing an important role as financial institutions cannot be separated from the problem of and credit provision would grow, because the activities of banks even as financial institutions, the provision of credit are the activities is the lowest of his, of the large number of credits already channeled will determine the size of the spider does not permit the. The condition of the amount of its credits micro small and medium enterprises (SMES) on a period of years of the observation of (period of 2012-2014) would be good enough.
2. The influence of savings to operational profit. From the regression be seen that savings have leverage significant and positive on operational profit on public credit bank Cirebon district. The outcome of the findings this explains that every an increase in savings will results in an increase of operational profit. To the increasing number of savings so company will be able to distribute credits with better, in addition there will be an increase operational income of interest income, provision, commission etc, who is the difference between the total cost of flowers to the total income flowers add operational profit, which in turn results in an increase of operational profit.

3. The influence of deposits to profit from the regression known that deposits its have leverage significant and positive on operational profit on public credit bank Cirebon district. The outcome of the findings this explains that every increased deposits will results in an increase of operational profit. This shows that the more large amount of the third party fund can collected by the bank the large amount of the profit be accepted. This is in accordance with the theory described by Taswan (2008) that to the increasing number of third party funds as a source of funds at bank, bank put these funds in the form of assets productive for example credit. Placement in the form of credits will contribute interest income for the bank who have an impact on profitability (profit).

V. The Conclusion

From the research and analysis of as a whole, writer can take conclusion as follows:

1. Credit variable, savings, deposits together/simultaneous significant impact on public credit bank operational profit Cirebon district. Adjusted value R^2 81,02 2 percent, the rest would belong to 18,98 percent described by other variables outside research.
2. Loans on a partial have had a positive impact and significant impact on operational profit on public credit bank Cirebon district.
3. Savings in partial have had a positive impact and significant impact on operational profit on public credit bank Cirebon district.
4. Deposits in partial have had a positive impact and significant impact on operational profit on public credit bank Cirebon district.

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